

**OXIDATIVE STEAM REFORMING AND STEAM REFORMING
OF METHANE, ISOCTANE AND *n*-TETRADECANE OVER AN
ALUMINA SUPPORTED SPINEL-DERIVED NICKEL CATALYST**

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Abstract

The present work is focused on analysing the potential of an alumina-supported spinel-derived nickel catalyst for oxidative steam reforming and steam reforming of model hydrocarbons present in gasoline and diesel, namely isooctane and *n*-tetradecane, respectively. For comparative purposes these reforming processes have been also investigated for methane and the catalytic behaviour of a commercial rhodium catalyst has been evaluated as well. When operating with a relatively high volume hourly space velocity (equivalent to $60000 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ C g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) at a low temperature ($600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) for 31 h time on stream, the activity of the investigated nickel catalyst is high and, more importantly, stable in the reforming of methane (either by steam reforming or oxidative steam reforming) and the oxidative steam reforming of isooctane. As for *n*-tetradecane a significant loss of activity with time on line is found, more pronounced under steam reforming conditions. Although the presence of oxygen helps in controlling coking, the reforming of this heavy feed unavoidably results in a substantial formation of graphitic filaments with a high chemical stability. Additionally, sintering and partial oxidation of the metallic phase have been also observed, mainly under oxidative steam reforming conditions. Finally, it can be concluded that, when compared with a commercial rhodium catalyst, the prepared nickel catalyst derived from NiAl_2O_4 is a more efficient reforming catalyst for fuels with varying chemical nature.

Keywords: nickel aluminate, methane, isooctane, n-tetradecane, oxidative steam reforming, coke

1. Introduction

The use of fuel cells for powering industries and vehicles is strongly conditioned by a reliable hydrogen infrastructure. Catalytic reforming of fuels is recognised as one main source for hydrogen supply for these devices.¹⁻³ Although renewable hydrocarbons are ideally preferred, fossil fuels can act as suitable feedstock for reforming in the short and medium term due to the already available distribution infrastructure. In this sense, high-density liquid fuels, like gasoline or diesel, are particularly attractive for on-board production of hydrogen for fuel cells.⁴⁻⁹

Conversion of hydrocarbon fuels (C_xH_y) to hydrogen can be typically performed by partial oxidation (POX, Ec. (1)) or steam reforming (SR, Ec. (2)). The first process is operationally simpler since it does not require water evaporation whereas the second one produces a larger yield of hydrogen. However, the hybrid process (oxidative steam reforming, OSR) that combines these two strategies (Ec.(3)) can be comparatively advantageous since it offers the possibility of energetically integrating the exothermic nature of partial oxidation and the endothermic nature of steam reforming by properly tuning the O_2/C_xH_y and H_2O/C_xH_y molar ratios while providing relatively H_2 -rich streams.⁹ Also the lower CO content provided by the OSR strategy may be highly desirable in order to minimise the size of the CO cleanup process necessary when operating with fuel cells susceptible to CO poisoning such as proton exchange membrane fuel cells.

In addition to the stability of the metallic phase, carbon deposition is probably the most important drawback in all catalytic technologies for reforming of hydrocarbons including oxidative reforming as well. This undesired phenomenon is especially relevant when processing heavy fuels since thermal cracking reactions can easily occur at relatively low temperatures and the formed by-products (mainly olefins) can induce the formation of carbonaceous deposits.¹⁰⁻¹² Apart from the type of hydrocarbon to be reformed carbon formation is also strongly dependent on the reaction temperature, the O/C and H₂O/C molar ratios, the flow rate of the fed fuel and the time span under reaction. Generally relatively lower flow rates, higher temperatures and excess of oxygen and water lead to limited carbon deposition.

It is widely accepted that noble metals exhibit a good reforming activity and are less prone to carbon formation but their implementation is very expensive.¹³⁻¹⁵ Alternatively nickel catalysts offer a good compromise between cost and catalytic behaviour in spite of the fact that its operation is frequently accompanied by coking.¹⁶⁻²⁰ It would be therefore of interest to develop nickel catalysts capable of ideally inhibiting coke formation or at least showing a high activity and a reasonable stability with time on stream although significant amounts of coke were formed on the catalyst. In this way an eventual operation-regeneration-operation cycle would be performed at as long as possible cycle time periods.

Most studies related to nickel reforming catalysts use nickel oxide as a precursor to obtain for active metallic nickel after reduction. An alternative approach for synthesis is to stabilise nickel within a well-defined crystalline oxide such as lanthanum nickelate (LaNiO₃)²¹ or nickel aluminate (NiAl₂O₄). As for this latter oxide phase a wide number of papers can be found in the literature dealing with the analysis of its potential for methane reforming by partial oxidation, steam reforming or dry reforming.²²⁻²⁷ In this sense we have

also evidenced the good behaviour of bulk nickel aluminate prepared by precipitation for various reforming processes including oxidative steam reforming as well.^{28,29} The interesting catalytic performance of this spinel is correlated with the relatively small Ni crystallite size that can be obtained after a reduction step at high temperatures (850 °C) and with a good thermal and textural stability when subjected to this severe thermal treatment.^{28,29} Moreover, this activation procedure advantageously provides thermally stabilised nickel samples with a high upper temperature limit (theoretically up to 850 °C) for operation if necessary, for example when running under a high volume hourly space velocity (VHSV).

With the aim of optimising the mass catalytic activity of nickel it seems reasonable to incorporate the spinel on a high surface support. Alumina can be considered a suitable candidate given the structural and chemical compatibility with reduced NiAl_2O_4 , which results in $\text{Ni}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$. Surprisingly few examples of $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ for reforming applications are available in the literature. These studies are focused on the steam reforming of methane over a $\text{Ni}/\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4/\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{alloy catalyst}$ ²⁴ and the steam reforming of diesel over a $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{YSZ catalyst}$.^{30,31} In this regard our recent results on this type of catalyst formulation pointed out that a $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalyst with a 17 wt.%Ni loading gives a comparable reforming activity than a bulk spinel sample (33 wt.%Ni), both prepared by precipitation, in the steam reforming of methane.³² It would be therefore of interest to further investigate the potential of this type of catalysts in the processing of representative hydrocarbons of common fuels (natural gas, gasoline and diesel) by steam reforming processes in the presence (OSR) or absence (SR) of oxygen in the feed. To the best of our knowledge no related studies have been published on this subject.

Hence, driven by the promising results found for our optimised 17 wt.%(Ni)NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ catalyst, in this work the viability of its use is investigated for the oxidative steam reforming of liquid fuels (namely isooctane, *i*-C₈H₁₈, and *n*-tetradecane, *n*-C₁₄H₃₀, typical molecules found in gasoline and diesel, respectively). The OSR conditions selected for this study can be ranked as soft conditions in terms of the relative abundance between the hydrocarbon and the added oxygen and water (O/C=1 and H₂O/C=3) but as more prone to coking on account of the relatively reaction temperature (600 °C) and the relatively high volume hourly space velocity employed (60000 cm³ C g⁻¹ h⁻¹). The catalyst has been evaluated during a reaction time interval of 31 hours. These operational parameters have been in order to allow meaningful reactivity and stability comparison of the investigated nickel catalyst. Hence the experiments have been intentionally run under conditions giving incomplete conversion and inducing coke deposition. A special attention has been paid on the reactivity of these heavy hydrocarbons in relation to that of methane, the effect of oxygen in the feed stream (by comparing steam and oxidative steam reforming processes) and the catalytic stability during prolonged time on stream including the characterisation of the spent samples as well. Results of a commercial Rh-based catalyst will be used as a reference for comparative purposes. Sulphur poisoning was not considered in this work.

2. Experimental

2.1. Catalysts preparation

The spinel-derived Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst has been synthesised by co-precipitation according to the following procedure. Hence, the process has been conducted by the drop-by-drop addition under constant stirring of a 0.6 M solution of NH₄OH into an aqueous slurry of a mixture of Ni(CH₃-COO)₂·4H₂O and Al(NO₃)₃·9H₂O (1:2 Ni/Al molar ratio) and crushed

γ -Al₂O₃ (133 m² g⁻¹, 0.3-0.5 mm, SA 6173, Saint-Gobain) to obtain 17 wt.% nickel loading. The temperature has been kept at 25 °C during the precipitation and the pH was fixed at 8. Afterwards the precipitates have been aged for 30 min before being filtered and washed with hot deionised water. The sample has been dried at 110 °C overnight and then calcined at 850 °C in static air for 4 h at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹. As a reference reforming catalyst, a commercial powdered Rh sample has been used (1%Rh/Al₂O₃, 132 m² g⁻¹, Alfa Aesar), which has been calcined at 700 °C in static air for 4 h with the same heating rate. Then pellets have been prepared by a process of compressing the powders into flakes in a hydraulic press (Specac), crushing and sieving (0.3-0.5 mm).

2.2. *Catalyst characterisation*

The nickel catalyst has been characterised by N₂ physisorption at -196 °C, wavelength dispersive X-ray fluorescence (WDXRF), X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), temperature programmed reduction with hydrogen (H₂-TPR) and temperature programmed desorption of NH₃ (NH₃-TPD). The spent samples have been thoroughly characterised by BET measurements, XRD, TEM, thermogravimetry coupled to mass spectrometry (TGA-MS), Raman spectroscopy and XPS. The experimental details of each analytical technique are described elsewhere.^{32,33}

2.3. *Catalytic tests*

The catalytic tests for oxidative steam reforming of the different hydrocarbons have been performed, on 125 mg of catalyst, in a flow reactor operating at atmospheric pressure at a constant temperature (600 °C) for 31 h. The reaction feed has consisted of a mixture of the selected hydrocarbon (15.6%CH₄, 1.9%*i*-C₈H₁₈ or 1.1%*n*-C₁₄H₃₀), oxygen and steam (with a O/C = 1 and H₂O/C = 3) diluted in N₂ with a total flow rate of 800 cm³ min⁻¹. Under these

conditions the carbon flow rate for the three fuels is identical ($5.6 \text{ mmol C min}^{-1}$). The catalytic results have been thus compared on the basis of an identical carbon-based volume hourly space velocity, namely $60000 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ C g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$, which corresponded to $60000 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ CH}_4 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$, $7500 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ } i\text{-C}_8\text{H}_{18} \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ and $4285 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ } n\text{-C}_{14}\text{H}_{30} \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$. Prior to the reaction, the nickel catalyst was activated by reduction with $5\% \text{ H}_2/\text{N}_2$ at $850 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 h whereas the rhodium catalyst was reduced at $700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ using the same reducing stream during the same time interval. Complementary catalytic runs have been also carried out in the absence of oxygen in order to explore the catalytic behaviour of the samples for steam reforming. In these experiments all the reaction conditions have been identical except for the fact that the addition of oxygen was suppressed. The liquid hydrocarbon (isooctane or *n*-tetradecane) and deionised water feeds have been delivered by two different HPLC pumps (Gilson) and have been vaporized separately, then mixed with the other gaseous components (O_2 and/or N_2) in heated gas lines. Both hot box and feed lines have been heated to a temperature of $180 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in order to vaporize the liquid feed. The obtained reaction products have been passed through a stainless steel cold water condenser to collect excess water and unreacted hydrocarbons before injection into the gas chromatograph. Therefore, dry gas stream at the outlet of the reactor was analysed online by a MicroGC (Agilent 3000) equipped with a TCD detector. Fuel conversion and yields to H_2 , CO , CO_2 and CH_4 have been determined according to the following equations:

$$X(\text{C}_x\text{H}_y), \% = \frac{F_{\text{out}}(\text{CO}) + F_{\text{out}}(\text{CO}_2) + F_{\text{out}}(\text{CH}_4)}{x \cdot F_{\text{in}}(\text{C}_x\text{H}_y)} \cdot 100 \quad (4)$$

$$Y(\text{H}_2) = \frac{F_{\text{out}}(\text{H}_2)}{0.5y \cdot F_{\text{in}}(\text{C}_x\text{H}_y) + F_{\text{in}}(\text{H}_2\text{O})} \quad (5)$$

$$Y(\text{CO}) = \frac{F_{\text{out}}(\text{CO})}{x \cdot F_{\text{in}}(\text{C}_x\text{H}_y)} \quad (6)$$

$$Y(\text{CO}_2) = \frac{F_{\text{out}}(\text{CO}_2)}{x \cdot F_{\text{in}}(\text{C}_x\text{H}_y)} \quad (7)$$

$$Y(\text{CH}_4) = \frac{F_{\text{out}}(\text{CH}_4)}{x \cdot F_{\text{in}}(\text{C}_x\text{H}_y)} \quad (8)$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Characterisation of the fresh sample

The results from the characterisation of the investigated catalysts are thoroughly discussed elsewhere.^{32,33} As a brief summary it must be pointed out that the precipitation route followed for synthesis results in a structurally homogeneous sample where the spinel is the main nickel phase after high-temperature calcination. No significant amounts of NiO are detected. This phase homogeneity has been verified by XRD (Figure 1 (a)) and XPS analysis (shown in electronic supporting info, Figure S1). The surface area of the calcined sample is 94 m² g⁻¹. On the other hand, H₂-TPR analysis confirms that the conversion of NiAl₂O₄ into Ni/Al₂O₃ expectedly requires temperatures as high as 850-900 °C (Figure S2). After reduction the transformation of Ni²⁺ ions of the spinel framework into metallic Ni is complete as revealed by the disappearance of the characteristic XRD diffraction signals attributed to the nickel aluminate structure (Figure 1 (b)). It is worth noting that this phase transformation involves a limited decrease in the surface area to 84 m² g⁻¹.

Figure 1

As evidenced by TEM analysis from the measurement of the size of 300 particles, the particle size distribution is characterised by a relatively symmetrical band. Most of the particles (99%) show a measured particle size lower than 20 nm (Figure S3). An average

size of 9.5 nm is thus estimated. This value is in good agreement with the mean size calculated by XRD from the Ni(200) signal at $2\theta = 52^\circ$ (9 nm). From this average particle size the corresponding values for nickel dispersion (33%) and specific nickel surface area ($40 \text{ m}^2_{\text{Ni}} \text{ g}^{-1}$) are estimated using the equations included in the electronic supporting information. Finally, the surface acidity has been characterised by means of temperature programmed desorption, using ammonia as probe molecule (NH_3 -TPD), followed by dynamic thermogravimetry coupled to mass spectrometry (Figure S4). The overall acidity of the reduced catalyst is $302 \mu\text{mol NH}_3 \text{ g}^{-1}$, significantly lower than that of the bare alumina support ($630 \mu\text{mol NH}_3 \text{ g}^{-1}$). The desorption profile reveals the presence of a band at low temperatures (175°C) accompanied by a second much more intense feature at relatively high temperatures (300°C), the latter being due to a notable fraction of strong acid sites (about 85%) present at the surface of the catalyst.

3.2 *Catalytic behaviour for OSR over the nickel catalyst*

Figure 2 shows the evolution of conversion in the oxidative steam reforming of the various hydrocarbons (methane, isooctane and *n*-tetradecane) with time on stream, at 600°C and $60000 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ C g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$, over the reduced spinel-derived nickel catalyst. The activity data corresponding to the commercial rhodium catalyst are also included for the sake of comparison. A stable behaviour is found for methane and isooctane along with a relatively high conversion (about 90% for methane and 80% for isooctane). When compared with the corresponding equilibrium values (94% and 100%, respectively, calculated by the HSC Chemistry software package using the GIBBS program) a better reforming efficiency for methane can be assessed. The rhodium catalyst also exhibits a good performance for methane oxidative steam reforming (75% conversion) but it is not so efficient for isooctane

(44%). Operating under a relatively similar volume hourly space velocity ($8600 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ } i\text{-C}_8\text{H}_{18} \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$), Kim et al.³⁴ found a slightly higher conversion at $700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ ($\text{O}/\text{C}=1$ and $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{C}=1.25$) over a 20 wt.%Ni/MgO catalyst. However, the sample displayed an unstable behaviour with an appreciable loss of activity from 86 to 80% in the time interval of 8 h. On the other hand, Chen et al.³⁵ synthesised a very active nickel catalyst (10 wt.%) supported on $\text{Ce}_{0.75}\text{Zr}_{0.25}\text{O}_2$ with an initial conversion of 82% at $650 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ under a space velocity as high as $20590 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ } i\text{-C}_8\text{H}_{18} \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$. After a time interval of 3 hours a marked deactivation is conversely seen as evidenced by the decrease in conversion from 82 to 70%, probably due to the low O/C and H₂O/C molar ratios ($\text{O}/\text{C}=0.5$ and $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{C}=1.8$) selected.

In the case of *n*-tetradecane a considerably lower reforming conversion over the spinel-derived nickel catalyst is observed when compared with isooctane (and obviously with methane). Thus, the initial conversion values at the beginning of the reaction are over 60% for the rhodium catalyst and 42% for the nickel catalyst. This trend in reforming reactivity of heavy hydrocarbons is consistent with the results reported by Kang et al.³⁶ who observed a favoured fuel conversion for hexane and isooctane (short chained hydrocarbons) with respect to *n*-dodecane and *n*-hexadecane (longer chained hydrocarbons) over a Gd-doped ceria supported platinum catalyst. In addition to the lower reactivity shown by *n*-tetradecane, the catalytic activity is not stable. Nevertheless, while conversion continuously decreases with time on stream from 60 to 30% over the noble metal catalyst, interestingly the nickel catalyst only shows a slight loss of activity from 42 to 38% during the first 5 h and then it reaches a stationary state with time on stream. Judging from these observations it is clear again that the synthesised nickel catalyst displays a better performance than the commercial catalyst, although at the cost of a rather larger metal loading.

It is also evident that that OSR reforming of this heavy hydrocarbon requires a considerably higher operation temperature and/or a lower VHSV. Indeed under these more favourable conditions a wide number of works reported reforming efficiencies for C₁₂-C₁₆ fuels in the range 60-100% over nickel catalysts. In this sense Gugilla et al.³⁷ found a 60% conversion (*n*-dodecane) over a 10%Ni/CeO₂/Al₂O₃ at 750 °C and 2400 cm³ *n*-C₁₂H₂₆ g⁻¹ h⁻¹. Substantially higher conversions (in the 90-100% range) are obtained with a lower VHSV by Kaila et al.³⁸ over a 12 wt.%Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst at 700 °C and 980 cm³ *n*-C₁₂H₂₆ g⁻¹ h⁻¹ (*n*-dodecane) and Xie et al.³⁹ with a 5 wt.%Ni/CeO₂ catalyst at 750 °C and 1500 cm³ *n*-C₁₆H₃₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹ (*n*-hexadecane). In these studies no results on the behaviour of the samples during extended time on stream are given.

Figure 2

Figure 2 also includes the evolution of the yield of the main reforming products (H₂, CO and CO₂) with time on stream corresponding to the OSR of the three fuels over the nickel and rhodium catalysts. In line with the observed reforming efficiency the yields are stable for OSR of methane and isooctane. As for Y(H₂) this is quite similar for these two hydrocarbons (0.47 for CH₄ and 0.35 for *i*-C₈H₁₈, respectively) and remarkably higher than that of the rhodium catalyst (0.31-0.10). Particularly the H₂ yield in methane OSR accounts for the 95% of the equilibrium value while this is 81% in isooctane reforming. In both cases a notable yield of CO₂ is also noted (0.6-0.7) whereas the CO yield is less pronounced (0.1-0.2). This could be explained by the limited activity of the catalyst in the reverse water gas shift reaction (CO₂+H₂→CO+H₂O) and/or the occurrence of the complete combustion reaction of the feed. Methane is also formed in the OSR of isooctane due to methanation reactions (Y(CH₄) = 0.06). In contrast, the H₂ yield of OSR of *n*-tetradecane decreases from

an initial value 0.13 to 0.08 after 31 h. CO₂ is also more abundant with respect to CO. Although methane is not observed in the product stream ethylene, propane and propylene are detected in the effluent stream (not quantified) as a result of cracking reactions on the acid surface of the catalyst.⁴⁰⁻⁴²

3.3. *Oxidative steam reforming vs steam reforming of heavy hydrocarbons*

In order to determine the effect of the role of oxygen in the reforming process of the three hydrocarbons additional experiments has been carried out for these hydrocarbons in the absence of oxygen over the nickel catalyst. In other words a comparison between steam reforming and oxidative steam reforming has been made. The used experimental conditions are identical in terms of temperature (600 °C), volume hourly space velocity (60000 cm³ C g⁻¹ h⁻¹), H₂O/C molar ratio (3) and time on stream (31 h). The corresponding results are plotted in Figure 3. Firstly it is observed that the nickel catalyst shows a stable behaviour in the steam reforming of methane with a conversion of 50%. Under OSR conditions the performance is stable as well but conversion is significantly higher (87%). As for isooctane OSR conversion is not only higher (81%) but also markedly more stable in comparison with steam reforming. Hence, for steam reforming an initial conversion of about 60% is obtained but this progressively decreases to about 42%.³³ In the case of *n*-tetradecane the differences in behaviour are less noticeable although a better performance could be assessed under OSR conditions as well. In addition to a lower initial conversion (22%) for steam reforming the activity slowly diminishes to about 17% after 31 hours.⁴³ It is then evident that the presence of oxygen enhanced the catalytic reforming efficiency. This promoting effect of oxygen in the reforming of heavy hydrocarbons is in agreement with the results reported by Guggllia et al. for *n*-dodecane. These authors observed a marked decrease in conversion from 65 to 40% in the steam reforming of this fuel at 800 °C

and a molar H₂O/C ratio of 2 over a 1 wt.%Ru/10%Ni/CeO₂/Al₂O₃ catalyst.⁴⁴ However, when adding oxygen to the feed stream (O/C=0.35) both catalytic activity and stability at the same reaction temperature are promoted since an almost constant higher conversion (70%) is obtained for 10 h-time on stream.³⁷

Figure 3

The product distribution for steam reforming is only stable for methane. A moderately lower H₂ yield (0.43, which corresponds to 71% of the equilibrium value) is obtained over the nickel catalyst with respect to OSR. Expectedly a higher yield of CO (0.35) is favoured at the expense of a lower yield of CO₂ (0.15). For heavier hydrocarbons the H₂ yield gradually diminishes with time to give values of 0.26 (isooctane) and 0.13 (*n*-tetradecane) at the end of the runs. Again the production of CO (0.16-0.26) is favoured over CO₂ (0.05-0.1). Similarly to OSR, methane (Y(CH₄) = 0.07) is formed in the steam reforming of isooctane and small hydrocarbons (C₂-C₄) are produced in the steam reforming of *n*-tetradecane.

3.4. *Characterisation of the post-run samples*

As stated previously the reforming process for methane over the nickel catalyst are quite stable with time on stream. When processing heavier hydrocarbons it is also evidenced that oxidative steam reforming results in a more favoured strategy with respect to steam reforming in terms of activity and stability. It is however important to determine the state of the used samples in order to define, on one hand, the causes of the observed decrease of activity in the steam reforming and, on the other hand, the relative importance of the changes in the samples used in OSR since these may eventually affect the catalytic behaviour for a more prolonged time on stream (>31 h). Hence, the spent catalysts have been thoroughly characterised by TGA-MS, TEM, BET measurements, XRD, Raman

spectroscopy and XPS so as to evaluate the extent of various potentially deactivating phenomena such as coking (amount of coke, its morphology, chemical nature and stability), nickel sintering and/or partial oxidation into NiO. Given the best results found for OSR the used samples in this reaction will be firstly discussed in more detail.

Figure 4 shows the derivative thermal gravimetric change versus temperature with a heating ramp of $1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$. While the oxidation profile of the nickel catalyst used in the reforming of methane is virtually flat (not shown), those corresponding to isooctane (Figure 4 (a)) and *n*-tetradecane (Figure 4 (b)) are characterised by a main broad peak at 530-540 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a shoulder at lower temperatures (450-460 $^{\circ}\text{C}$). After integrating the area under the curves the amount of deposited coke is quantified (24 and 37 wt.% for *i*-C₈H₁₈ and *n*-C₁₄H₃₀, respectively) (Table 1). TEM analysis evidences that the samples are mainly covered with filamentous carbon (Figure 5). The combustion temperatures found in the thermogravimetric runs are in agreement with those expected for carbon with this filamentous morphology.^{31,45} Note that the presence of coating carbon in the form of CH_x carbonaceous species is ruled out in view of the absence of combustion peaks at lower temperatures and the absence of water as a combustion product as determined by on-line MS analysis of gaseous products during thermogravimetric analysis.

In addition to the greater tendency of *n*-tetradecane to coke deposition, substantial differences are observed regarding the stability of the carbonaceous deposits as well. Quantitative estimation of deposited carbon indicated that, while 95% of the coke formed during isooctane reforming requires combustion temperatures below 550 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, it is only around 60% for *n*-tetradecane thereby suggesting the presence of carbon with a superior stability.⁴² It should be pointed out that although the amount of deposited coke during the isooctane reforming is considerable (24 wt.%), this does not seem to significantly affect the

catalytic conversion over time. It can be then assumed that the accessibility of the metallic phase is not blocked.³¹ On the other hand, it must be pointed out that the used Rh catalyst also contained substantial amounts of coke. Indeed, the specific formation (3.4 and 18.5 g_C g_{Rh}⁻¹ in isooctane and *n*-tetradecane oxidative steam reforming, respectively) is significantly higher than that noticed over Ni catalyst (1.4 and 2.2 g_C g_{Ni}⁻¹, in isooctane and *n*-tetradecane oxidative steam reforming, respectively).

Figure 4/Figure 5/Table 1

The specific surface area of the post-run catalysts (Table 1) is relatively similar (91 m² g⁻¹ for *i*-C₈H₁₈ and 82 m² g⁻¹ for *n*-C₁₄H₃₀) to that of the fresh sample (84 m² g⁻¹). This suggests that the eventual blockage of the pores of the catalyst is compensated by the contribution of the porosity of the deposited coke. On the other hand, according to the observed characteristic signal of graphitic coke at 2θ = 26.3° in the XRD profiles (Figure 1 (d) and (e)), some of the filaments are graphitic. These results are consistent with those reported by Chen et al.³⁵ who also found a strong graphitic peak in the oxidative steam reforming of isooctane over a 15 wt.%Ni/Ce_{0.75}Zr_{0.25}O₂ catalyst with a carbon accumulation of 88 wt.%.

In an attempt to gain insight into the nature of the carbonaceous deposits, the used nickel catalysts have been further characterised by Raman spectroscopy (Figure 6). The obtained results reveal, on one hand, the negligible formation of carbonaceous deposits with methane (not shown) and, on the other hand, the simultaneous presence of both defective or unstructured coke (Band D, 1320 cm⁻¹; Band D', 1605 cm⁻¹) and graphitic or more structured coke (Band G, 1580 cm⁻¹) with the heavy hydrocarbons.⁴⁶⁻⁵¹ The high intensity of both signals is in line with the observed notable amounts of coke by TGA-MS. The ratio

of the area of the D band to that of the G band (I_D/I_G) can be regarded as an index for the crystalline order of deposited coke.³³ Thus, the I_D/I_G value has been calculated from curve fitting of each Raman spectrum shown in Figure 6 (a) using three Lorentzian lines for three bands (D, D' and G). The obtained values are 1.7 and 2.0 for isooctane and *n*-tetradecane, respectively (Table 1), which suggest that the presence of oxygen in the reaction environment tends to induce the formation of coke with a predominant amorphous character.

Figure 6

Finally, the XPS C 1s spectra of carbon species on the spent Ni-based catalysts are shown in Figure 7. The profiles are dominated by a strong contribution of graphitic-like carbon at 284.5 eV. With a much lower abundance the peak at 285.3 eV is related to defective graphitic-like carbon whereas the bands at higher binding energy (286.2-287.5 eV) are attributed to deeply oxidised carbonaceous residues adsorbed on the catalyst surface.⁵²⁻⁵⁴ On the other hand, the absence of metal carbide formation (NiC_x), at 280.6-282.6 eV is corroborated in agreement with XRD analysis. Indeed XRD analysis of the spent samples (Figure 1 (d) and (e)) also indicates a slight sintering (from 9 to 12 nm, as estimated by Ni(200) diffraction line) during isooctane reforming. However, a much more considerable increase in nickel crystallite size (by a factor of 3, 30 nm) is found for the sample used in the reforming of *n*-tetradecane. Besides the partial oxidation of the active phase into inactive NiO also occurs as evidenced by the signal at $2\theta = 43.3^\circ$. Therefore, the NiO/Ni(200) XRD intensity ratio, taken as a semiquantitative evidence for nickel oxidation, is 1.0 and 1.3 for isooctane and *n*-tetradecane reforming, respectively. These two phenomena, namely nickel sintering and partial oxidation, are more pronounced for

n-tetradecane probably due to its larger heat of combustion (8820 kJ mol⁻¹) in comparison with isooctane (5114 kJ mol⁻¹), which may provoke hot spots at the surface of the catalyst thereby resulting in the aforementioned sintering and oxidation to nickel oxide. In sum the slight decrease in conversion with time on stream found in the oxidative steam reforming of this hydrocarbon can be associated with a combination of increased coking and lower thermal and chemical stability of metallic nickel.

Figure 7

On the other hand, the characterisation of the nickel catalyst used in OSR of methane (Table 1) clearly indicates a good textural stability (no change in surface area) and a very low tendency to coking (as revealed by TGA-MS and Raman spectroscopy) and sintering (as revealed by XRD (Figure 1 (c))). Only the presence of NiO is noticed but it does not apparently induce an alteration of the catalytic behaviour with time on line.

Compared with OSR, steam reforming of both isooctane and *n*-tetradecane is characterised by the formation of considerably larger amounts of coke (67 and 73 wt.%, respectively) (Table 1), which in turn induces a marked increase in surface area of the used samples (from 84 m² g⁻¹ for the fresh sample to 108-123 m² g⁻¹ for the used samples) probably due to its high porosity. When compared with the observed lower coke deposition under OSR conditions, it is therefore reasonable to think that the presence of oxygen is helpful to limit the formation of coke.^{16,55-58} Furthermore, the stability of these carbonaceous deposits is also higher as revealed by the higher oxidation peak temperature (560-570 °C) with respect to the combustion of coke from OSR (530 °C) (Figure 4). Additionally, in view of the comparatively lower I_D/I_G ratios (1.2-1.6), the coke formed during steam reforming is more graphitic, in line with the higher temperatures required for combustion (Figure 6). Therefore it can be concluded that when water is exclusively used as an oxidant for

reforming, the formed coke tends to be thermally more stable and structured (with a concomitant lower I_D/I_G value). On the other hand, nickel sintering is not very marked with respect to OSR (with an increase in crystallite size up to 11-15 nm) (Figure 1 (g) and (h)). On the other hand, it worth pointing out that the larger amounts of highly structured of coke formed during OSR of *n*-tetradecane probably acted as efficient barrier for water diffusion, thereby partially avoiding the oxidation of metallic nickel. As a result the NiO/Ni0(200) XRD intensity ratio is relatively low (1.0). Hence, the poorer behaviour of the nickel catalyst for steam reforming can be essentially related to coking as the thermal and chemical stability of nickel phase is altered to a relatively small extent. To end up, just to mention that the physico-chemical properties of the nickel catalyst used in the steam reforming of methane remain virtually unaffected (Table 1).

4. Conclusions

The feasibility of a co-precipitated alumina supported NiAl₂O₄-based catalyst (with a nickel loading of 17 wt.%) in the oxidative steam reforming of a variety of hydrocarbons (methane, isooctane and *n*-tetradecane) operating at a relatively high weight hourly space velocity has been confirmed. Both high activity and stability are found for methane and isooctane, whereas *n*-tetradecane evidences considerably lower reforming characteristics. The exhibited good performance of the investigated nickel catalyst is related to its high metallic surface area and low crystallite size.

The use of hydrocarbons heavier than methane presents an increased risk of carbon formation (24 and 37 wt.% for isooctane and *n*-tetradecane, respectively) after a reaction time interval of 30 hours. However, the impact of coking on catalytic behaviour is clearly different depending on the feed. Hence, although the carbon accumulation in the reforming

of isooctane is considerable this does not result in an apparent decrease in conversion and hydrogen yield with time on stream compared with that of *n*-tetradecane. Deposited coke is mainly formed by graphitic filaments with a superior chemical stability in the case of the reforming of *n*-tetradecane. Observed changes in the metallic phase such as partial oxidation of nickel and sintering can also play a negative role in the catalytic behaviour. The comparative analysis with steam reforming points out that this process is only efficient (with high and stable H₂ yields) for methane. Hence a gradual decrease in activity is evident for isooctane and *n*-tetradecane, which is associated with a more favoured formation of stable coke due to the absence of oxygen in the feedstream.

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Supporting information

Supporting information associated with this article can be found in the online version.

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CAPTIONS FOR TABLES AND FIGURES

- Table 1 Physico-chemical characterisation of the used spinel-derived nickel catalyst in various hydrocarbons reforming reactions.
- Figure 1 XRD patterns of the spinel-derived nickel catalyst: (a) calcined sample, (b) reduced sample and used samples in oxidative steam reforming of (c) methane, (d) isooctane and (e) *n*-tetradecane and used in steam reforming of (f) methane, (g) isooctane and (h) *n*-tetradecane. ((•) Ni⁰, (■) NiAl₂O₄, (▲) NiO, (✦) Al₂O₃, (★) graphitic coke).
- Figure 2 Catalytic performance of the spinel-derived nickel and rhodium catalysts in terms of C_xH_y conversion and H₂, CO, and CO₂ yield with time on stream at 600 °C for oxidative steam reforming of CH₄, *i*-C₈H₁₈ and *n*-C₁₄H₃₀. Reaction conditions: W = 0.125 g; 60000 cm³ C g⁻¹ h⁻¹; Gas mixture: 15.6%CH₄, 1.9%*i*-C₈H₁₈ and 1.1%*n*-C₁₄H₃₀ with H₂O/C = 3, O/C = 1 and balance with N₂.
- Figure 3 Catalytic performance of the spinel-derived nickel catalyst in terms of C_xH_y conversion and H₂, CO, and CO₂ yield with time on stream at 600 °C for steam reforming of CH₄, *i*-C₈H₁₈ and *n*-C₁₄H₃₀. Reaction conditions: W = 0.125 g; 60000 cm³ C g⁻¹ h⁻¹; Gas mixture: 15.6%CH₄, 1.9%*i*-C₈H₁₈ and 1.1%*n*-C₁₄H₃₀ with H₂O/C = 3 and balance with N₂.
- Figure 4 Evolution of the inverted DTG signal with the combustion temperature of the used spinel-derived nickel catalysts, (a) for isooctane and (b) for *n*-tetradecane.

Figure 5 TEM images of the used spinel-derived nickel catalysts, (a) for isooctane and (b) for *n*-tetradecane oxidative steam reforming.

Figure 6 Raman spectra of the used spinel-derived nickel catalysts, (a) for isooctane and (b) for *n*-tetradecane.

Figure 7 XPS C 1s spectra of the used spinel-derived nickel catalysts, (a) for isooctane and (b) for *n*-tetradecane oxidative steam reforming.

	Used in OSR			Used in SR		
	CH ₄	<i>i</i> -C ₈ H ₁₈	<i>n</i> -C ₁₄ H ₃₀	CH ₄	<i>i</i> -C ₈ H ₁₈	<i>n</i> -C ₁₄ H ₃₀
S _{BET} , m ² g ^{-1,a}	86	91	82	83	123	108
Ni ⁰ size, nm ^b	11	12	30	11	11.5	15.5
NiO/Ni ⁰ (200) ^b	0.6	1	1.3	--	1.5	1
Coke, wt.% ^c	--	24	37	--	67	71
C/Ni ⁰ (111) ^b	--	0.8	0.8	--	4.3	2.8
I _D /I _G ^d	--	1.7	2	--	1.6	1.2

^a Determined by N₂ physisorption (Freshly reduced sample = 84 m² g⁻¹).

^b Estimated by XRD analysis from Ni⁰ (200) diffraction line (Freshly reduced sample = 9 nm).

^c Determined by TGA-MS analysis.

^d Determined by Raman spectroscopy.

Table 1

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Spinel derived
Ni-catalyst

H₂ (T > 825 °C)

High metallic surface area
Low crystallite size

Benefits of OSR vs SR

600 °C; 60000 cm³ C g⁻¹ h⁻¹

- ✓ Higher H₂ yield for CH₄ and *i*-C₈H₁₈
- ✓ Less CO formation
- ✓ Better stability (minor coke deposition)

TOC GRAPHIC